

Relationship between Principals' Transformational Leadership Style and Teachers' Job Commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Kitui County, Kenya

Dorcus Nthenya Kimuyu¹, Susan Chepkonga², Jeremiah M. Kalai³

¹Postgraduate Student, University of Nairobi

²Lead Supervisor and Associate Professor, Faculty of Education, University of Nairobi

³Supervisor and Professor, Faculty of Education, University of Nairobi

ABSTRACT: This study explored the relationship between principals' transformational leadership style and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County, Kenya. Anchored on Transformational Leadership Theory, the study employed a convergent parallel mixed-methods design integrating descriptive and phenomenological approaches. The target population included 410 schools, 410 principals, 410 deputy principals, and 2,417 teachers. A sample of 243 schools and 343 teachers was obtained using Taro Yamane's formula. Data collection utilised questionnaires and interview guides, with quantitative data analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, and qualitative data analysed thematically. Findings revealed that transformational leadership significantly predicted teachers' affective and continuance commitment, but not normative commitment. The study recommends strengthening principal leadership training and enhancing inclusive leadership practices.

KEY WORDS: Demographics, Transformational leadership style, Teachers' job commitment

INTRODUCTION

School leadership is vital in influencing educational results and improving student success. School leaders are vital in tackling equity and access challenges, guaranteeing that every student gets the assistance and resources required for success, irrespective of their background. Transformational leaders inspire and motivate staff and students, while instructional leaders focus on curriculum, teaching quality, and professional development (Li & Liu, 2022). Chen and Chen (2022) identified notable discrepancies in leadership styles utilized in Germany and China. The authors indicate that principals in Germany investigated transformational, instructional, and integrated leadership styles, while in China, they examined transformational and instructional leadership styles to fulfill their schools' goals. The research also found that, in contrast to Germany, transformational and instructional leadership significantly enhance student achievement in China. Duyan and Yildiz (2020) suggested that transformational leadership is a crucial tool that helps academic personnel in Turkey realize their potential by enhancing job satisfaction, inspiring them to demonstrate extra-role behavior, and even pushing their boundaries to achieve superior performance (Weller, Süß, Evanschitzky, & Von Wangenheim, 2019). In Malaysia, the leadership styles of principals affect the school climate and the success of students. A guide on transformational leadership in overseeing the school atmosphere, particularly in enhancing teacher dedication and student academic achievement, has been established (Ibrahi et al., 2021).

Demir (2018) findings on transformational leadership and collective efficacy in the USA indicate that transformational leaders who engage in individual consideration (IC) create a nurturing teaching and learning atmosphere. The school principal pays close attention to each teacher's professional and personal requirements, offering collaborative assistance. These enhance personal effectiveness and efficiency regarding students' successful academic outcomes in national state examinations. Additionally, research conducted by Hattie (2019) regarding students' academic success in Egypt revealed that school leaders who engage in transformational leadership act as exemplary figures who are appreciated, revered, and relied upon by their followers. This stimulates, energizes, and motivates followers so that the connection between leaders and followers relies on personal comprehension rather than official, institutional guidelines, regulations, incentives, and penalties.

In Nigeria, Wakkala, Danjuma, and Aliyu (2022) concluded that transformational leadership was the most common leadership styles in public secondary schools. This leadership style has significantly influenced teacher performance. In Rwanda Asiimwe

and Zuena (2023), found that disagreement between head teachers and their teachers occur in schools because of the leadership style they apply in their schools, like; teachers' absenteeism, persistence in drinking alcohol during working hours, are related to head teachers' leadership style. Yuya (2020) noted that the transactional leadership approach is more prevalent among school leaders in Ethiopia. The school leaders lacked the drive to foster and sustain the teachers' dedication to effective teaching and school improvement. Teachers viewed their principals as lacking initiative and engagement in adapting to reforms and changes within their schools. The students, educators, and school administrators lacked the visionary qualities needed to successfully drive the school reform and transformation.

The leadership approaches employed by school principals influence students' futures and consequently affect school performance (Ismail, 2022). In Kenya, principals serve as leaders and managers of everything that occurs in schools. They are responsible for implementing educational strategies that promote efficient teaching and learning in schools. In Kenya, the primary responsibility of principals is to maintain academic excellence among their students by prioritizing teaching and learning based on measurable performance of both students and teachers. The school principals bear the primary responsibility of guiding all school activities towards the established objectives by effectively overseeing all learning processes (Mukiri, Njati, & Thurania, 2024). In Kenya, the school head is the chief educator and financial officer, tasked with the operational management of the institution.

Statement of the Problem

Despite substantial government investment in teacher recruitment and remuneration, teacher job commitment in Kitui County remains low. Reports indicate frequent absenteeism, delayed reporting, and high turnover intentions among teachers, particularly non-locals. Existing studies in Kenya seldom address teacher commitment within ASAL contexts, hence a gap in understanding how leadership styles contribute to commitment levels. This study investigated the relationship between principals' transformational leadership and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County.

Transformational Leadership Theory

The concept of Transformational Leadership Theory was introduced by James MacGregor Burns in 1978. Bernard Bass further expanded the theory in 1985. Burns characterized leadership as a combination of three behaviors: leaders' capacity to inspire followers, referred to as charismatic leadership; collaborating with followers on a personal level to address individual needs, known as individualized consideration; and encouraging creativity and diligent problem-solving, termed intellectual stimulation. Transformational Leadership signifies effective strategic leadership that must resonate with both the personal interests of their team members and their collective social interests (Kemal & Surji, 2015). Transformational Leadership merges charismatic, personalized influence (offering the vision, promoting high standards, motivating the followers) with instrumental, competence-driven professionalism (Andersen, 2015)

Transformational leadership theory examines the impactful actions of leaders and the influence of those actions on the performance of their followers (Ciulla, 2014). Transformational leaders impact their followers through outstanding actions, motivation, and a selfless mindset. Transformational leaders exhibit strong leadership through their actions and inspire their followers' dedication to the organization's objectives. Transformational leadership is a leadership approach focused on boosting employees' motivation to meet organizational objectives (Priest & Gass, 2017). The idea of transformational leadership unifies various elements of innovative vision and action, encompassing cognitive aspects, organizational changes, enhancement of capabilities, and the incorporation of dynamic capabilities theory within organizations. Transformational leaders serve as change agents, shifting organizations from outdated frameworks to new perspectives on their vision and mission strategies. They serve as role models to their followers, which subsequently improves organizational performance (Effelsberg et al., 2014).

Transformational leaders aim to enhance determination, foster long-term commitments, and promote mutual interests, built upon shared interdependence and everyone's readiness to prioritize organizational goals over individual interests (Ogolla, 2020). Transformational leadership is typically receptive to innovation, perceives sudden shifts in the business landscape, which necessitate drastic alterations in the organization. Transformational leaders view themselves as catalysts for change and inspire their followers. In contrast to transactional leaders, who utilize their authority by incentivizing employees with rewards and recognition, transformational leaders inspire their followers and guide them toward a vision or aspiration for improved performance (Creswell, 2014). The transformational leadership approach primarily focuses on motivating employees to enhance

their performance. Consequently, the staff adopts the aims and targets of the organization, which provides them with intrinsic motivation to strive for enhancing overall organizational performance (Kreitner & Kinicki 2015). The theory is relevant in this study in that the transformational leaders in secondary schools will not only provide the staff with a vision and share a common goal, but also give them consideration and stimulate their capacity in work. Principals in Kenyan secondary schools operate within a hierarchical, resource-constrained system, the theory’s emphasis on vision, innovation, and personalized support addresses critical challenges like teacher disengagement and turnover.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Variables

A conceptual framework shows that principal’s transformational leadership style can affect teacher affective, normative, and continuance commitment. However, the strength of this relationship may be affected by the intervening variable which is the provision of leadership in public secondary schools.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a convergent parallel mixed-methods design, utilizing a descriptive quantitative survey and a phenomenological qualitative interview component. The study targeted 410 public secondary schools. The population comprised of 410 principals, 410 deputy principals and 2417 teachers. Stratified was used to sample 243 public secondary school, 243 principals and 343 teachers. Purposive sampling was used to sample 41 deputy principals. Conducting in-depth interviews (45–70 minutes each), transcribing, and performing rigorous thematic analysis on 243 interviews would have been unrealistic within the scope of this study. A sample of 41 is within the commonly recommended range for qualitative studies (10-50 respondents) as recommended by (Guest et al., 2006; Hageman & Wutich, 2017). Inclusion of only 41 deputy principals is not statistically disproportionate but methodologically justified. The study used questionnaires for principals and teachers while data from the deputy principals was collected using interview guides. Quantitative data (questionnaires) captures measurable trends and relationships between leadership styles and types of teacher commitment (affective, continuance, and normative) while qualitative data (interview guides) provides rich, contextual insights into how and why certain leadership behaviors influence teacher attitudes and experiences. The use of both methods allows for triangulation, increasing the findings’ credibility and trustworthiness. Using both designs allow the researcher to answer different types of questions simultaneously. In this study, content and construct validity was used. Content validity was improved through professional judgment to ensure that the questionnaires would help to achieve study objectives. The use of professionals in education was to ensure that the questionnaire was assessed by education experts. Construct validity on the other hand ensured that the variable metrics in the conceptual framework were replicated in the questionnaire. Reliability was tested using Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient and the threshold for reliability was met. Data was analysed using SPSS Version 28. The analysis was based on descriptive and inferential statistics.

Descriptives included mean and standard deviation. The mean showed the average number of respondents agreeing/disagreeing with statements in the questionnaire and the standard deviation showed variability of the mean. A low standard deviation shows that data points are grouped closely near the mean, while a high standard deviation shows that data points are dispersed. The inferential statistics used in the study was regression which helped to establish how changes in the independent variable would predict changes in the dependent variable. The regression was also used to test the study hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study sought to explore the nexus between principal’s transformational leadership style and teachers’ levels of job commitment in public Schools in Kitui County. Principals and teachers were asked to indicate the extent to which they disagree/agree with statements related to principals’ transformational leadership style. Findings are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Transformational Leadership Style

Statements	Principals (n=184)		Teachers(n=312)	
	M	Std.	M	Std.
The principals;				
Idealized influence dimension				
Allow teachers offering different points of view	3.95	1.374	3.38	1.393
Give equal chance to teachers to speak in meetings	3.89	1.380	2.53	1.498
Encourage teachers to express their opinion	3.93	1.363	3.41	1.332
Involve teachers in decision making process	3.91	1.277	4.13	1.179
Respect teachers’ personal rights in work place	4.04	1.234	4.70	0.500
Give equal training opportunities to all teachers	4.08	1.297	2.58	1.580
Inspirational motivation dimension				
Encourage exceptionally high standards of performance	4.43	1.099	4.78	0.416
Establish clear priorities	4.35	1.061	4.26	0.515
Ask questions to clarify ideas	4.30	0.741	4.42	0.494
Set specific standards for task achievement	3.24	1.497	4.39	0.545
Demonstrate passion for excellence in every aspect of work	3.31	1.325	4.05	0.505
Assign specific tasks to teachers	3.41	1.177	4.43	0.779
Intellectual stimulation dimension				
Express hopes about solution of problem	3.59	1.388	4.76	0.428
Encourage teachers to generate alternative solutions to the problem	4.79	0.727	4.41	0.493
Hold consultative discussion in groups to highlight the school strengths	3.99	1.197	4.57	0.509
Try new approaches to accomplish our tasks in target time	3.78	1.181	4.39	0.521
Suggest new ways to complete our assignments	3.83	1.277	2.16	0.513
Encourage thoughtful risk-taking	3.79	1.166	4.20	0.473
Individualized consideration dimension				
Make individual teachers feel important	3.80	1.342	3.21	1.384
Aid teachers to acquire necessary knowledge	3.49	1.422	3.42	1.117
Get involved in assessment of teachers’ training needs	3.45	1.436	4.68	0.560
Provide helpful career advice to teachers	4.22	1.306	4.08	0.711
Involve teachers in making decisions that affect them	4.19	1.302	3.26	1.467
Listen to teachers with great courtesy	4.26	0.538	4.36	0.557
Average	3.92	1.230	3.96	0.811

The researcher identifies some similarities and differences from the findings. Both the principals and the teachers strongly agree on inspirational motivation dimension of transformational leadership. This reflects shared recognition of the principal’s ability to set high performance standards, clarify priorities, and demonstrate passion for excellence. Teachers confirm that the principals encourage exceptionally high standards, and assign specific tasks while the principals reported similar engagement in the behaviours. Additionally, respondents concurred that the principals listen with courtesy, and express hope in problem-solving. This shows mutual perceived strength in motivational and communicative leadership. This suggests that vision-setting and goal-oriented behaviours are visible, consistent, and valued across the school hierarchy.

The respondents however disagreed on the idealized influence and intellectual stimulation. Teachers rated principals much lower on providing equal training opportunities and same chances to address issues during meetings,. This shows a critical disconnect in perceived fairness and inclusivity. While the teachers strongly disagree that principals suggest new ways to complete assignments, the principal rated this perception moderately. In addition, teachers acknowledge involvement in decision-making; they feel less individually valued in comparison to the principals who feel that they adequately involve teachers in decision making. The differences show a self-perception bias among principals and a teacher-experienced deficit in equity, innovation visibility, and personal consideration. Results concur with Muthusi, Okoth, Chepkonga, & Okumbe (2024) and Sirait, Suriansyah, and Ngadimun (2021) that principals who possess supervisory skills, a strong need for achievement, intelligence, assertiveness, self-confidence, and initiative can motivate teachers to perform at their best. Such principals are able to encourage subordinates to solve problems carefully and rationally. Findings are also in agreement with Shafi et al. (2020) that leaders who practice inspirational motivation are able to apply high standards and also encourage subordinates to reach these standards. The leaders are also able to generate optimism and high enthusiasm from the people they lead. Yu et al. (2022) supported the assertion that transformational leadership indirectly reduces the likelihood of teachers leaving the profession by enhancing overall job satisfaction.

Table 2: Teachers’ Job Commitment

Statements	Teachers(n=312)	
	M	Std.
Affective Commitment		
I accomplish my duties on time	2.20	1.011
I feel proud to work in this school	2.29	0.928
I am willing to put in extra effort to help my school succeed	4.18	0.604
I feel emotionally attached to my teaching job	3.89	1.223
Continuance Commitment		
Leaving this school would require considerable personal sacrifice	4.18	0.899
I have good relationships and benefits in this schools that would be hard to replace at another school	4.03	0.869
It would be costly for me to leave this job	4.41	0.885
One of the main reasons I continue to work here is the stability it provides.	4.31	0.941
Normative Commitment		
I have a sense of duty to continue working at this school	2.01	0.945
Even if I received a better job offer elsewhere, I would not leave this school	1.89	1.147
I feel that I owe it to this school to continue working here	4.14	0.837
This schools have given me so much and it would be wrong to leave	2.03	1.044
Average	3.38	1.156

The findings assess teachers' affective commitment, their emotional attachment, sense of belonging, and willingness to contribute to the school. The results indicate mixed levels of commitment, with some areas showing strong engagement while others suggest dissatisfaction or disengagement. With respect to affective commitment, teachers do not feel proud of working at the school and struggle with timely task completion, indicating low motivation and possible dissatisfaction with leadership or working conditions. Despite challenges, teachers remain dedicated to their profession and are willing to dedicate more time and efforts for the success of the school. The gap between professional passion and institutional dissatisfaction suggests a risk of teacher burnout or attrition if school leadership does not address their concerns.

Regarding continuance commitment, teachers remain at the school due to financial, social, and job security reasons rather than intrinsic motivation or emotional attachment. High dependency on stability suggests that teachers may not be fully engaged or satisfied with their roles but feel compelled to stay due to personal sacrifices associated with leaving. The school benefits from teacher retention, but low job satisfaction and motivation could impact productivity, innovation, and commitment levels over time.

Results on normative commitment show that teachers are dissatisfied with the school which increases the risk of turnover. There is also high mobility whereby teachers would leave if a better opportunity arises, highlighting job dissatisfaction or lack of strong attachment to the institution. While some teachers acknowledge that the school has contributed to their growth, this feeling is not strong enough to retain them. The deputy principals also commented on teacher job commitment. Deputy Principals reported that some teachers arrive at school late, which could indicate poor time management, lack of motivation, or lenient enforcement of punctuality policies. They also indicated that some teachers lack professional competence, which affects their ability to prepare necessary documents on time. Others are labelled as lazy, implying that non-compliance may not always stem from a lack of ability but rather poor work ethic and attitude. Deputy Principals notes that most teachers regularly give assignments, showing that they recognize the importance of student engagement beyond the classroom. However, some teachers fail to meet deadlines, creating administrative challenges. Failure to meet deadlines affects school administration, making it harder for principals to ensure smooth academic operations. Although teachers perform well in some areas, their lateness, poor planning, and delayed professional record-keeping are key areas of concern. Some teachers struggle with professional competencies, requiring additional training or mentorship. Findings are in agreement with Bett, Allida, and Mendoza (2020) indicate that dedicated educators are deeply committed to their roles and significantly motivate their students. A dedicated teacher is also dedicated to the school by investing personal time to actively participate in the community and school activities.

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to explore the nexus between principal's transformational leadership style and three dimensions of teacher commitment (affective, continuance, normative). Results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Transformational Leadership Style and Teacher Commitment

Teacher Commitment	(M ± SD)	F-value	df	p-value
Affective commitment	36.75 ± 2.61	1.77	(24, 285)	.017
Continuance commitment	16.93 ± 1.63	1.84	24, 285)	.011
Normative commitment	10.06 ± 2.67	1.09	(24, 285)	.359

The results show that principal's transformational leadership style significantly predicts affective and continuance commitment among teachers' ($p = .017$ & $p = .011$) but not normative commitment ($p = .359$). Teachers under transformational leaders report stronger emotional attachment and lower intentions to leave suggesting that inspirational, intellectually stimulating, and individually considerate leadership enhances intrinsic motivation and teacher retention. However, feelings of obligation are less affected implying that duty-based loyalty relies more on the school norms than the behavior of the principals. This suggests that although transformational principals can reduce turnover by making teaching more fulfilling, institutional norms and long-term policies are needed to cultivate obligation.

Regression analysis was conducted to understand how a unit change in principal's transformational leadership style may cause a change in teachers' job commitment. Findings are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Model Summary for Transformational Leadership and Job Commitment

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.544 ^a	0.296	0.292	1.284

a. Predictors: (Constant), transformational leadership

As indicated in Table 4, the R-squared for the relationship between principal’s transformational leadership style and teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County was 0.296; this is an indication that at a 95% confidence interval, 29.6% of the variation in the teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County can be attributed to changes in the transformational leadership style. Therefore, the transformational leadership style can be used to explain 29.6% of changes in the teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County. The findings show that a transformational leadership style can explain changes in teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County. Transformational principals foster a strong emotional connection between teachers and the school by creating a shared vision and cultivating a sense of purpose. Teachers feel valued and part of a meaningful mission, which enhances their loyalty and emotional investment in their work. Results support Nguni et al, (2016) and Muthusi, Okoth, Chepkonga, & Okumbe (2024) that transformational leadership significantly fosters teachers' affective commitment through shared goals and a positive work environment. Rovida (2019) also found that transformational leadership positively affect teachers’ work culture.

Table 5: ANOVA for Transformational Leadership Style and Job Commitment

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	126.136	1	126.1.648	76.536	.000 ^b
Residual	299.946	182	.485		
Total	426.082	183			

a. Dependent Variable: teachers’ job commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), transformational leadership style

The ANOVA findings in Table 5 suggest that the model used in the study was a good fit for predicting the teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County. The probability value (Prob>F_{1,183} = 0.000) being less than the 0.05 significance level indicates that the model was significant, and the F-calculated value (76.536) being greater than the F-critical value shows that transformational leadership style is a significant predictor of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County. These results align with earlier studies that have emphasized the significance of a transformational leadership approach in enhancing teachers’ commitment to their jobs. For example, research conducted by Lee, Aydin, and Cilek (2019) demonstrated that transformational leadership positively affects organizational commitment since teachers feel valued and regarded as essential contributors to the school's success.

Table 6: Beta Coefficients for Transformational Leadership Style and Job Commitment

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	β	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.354	.325		4.172	.000
Transformational leadership	.673	.077	.544	8.748	.000

a. Dependent Variable: teachers’ job commitment

From the results in Table 6, the following regression model was fitted.

$$Y = 1.354 + 0.673 X_1$$

(X_1 is transformational leadership style)

The coefficient results showed that the constant had a coefficient of 1.354, suggesting that if the transformational leadership style was held constant at zero, the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County would be 1.354 units. In addition, results showed that the transformational leadership style coefficient was 0.673, indicating that a unit increase in transformational leadership style would result in a 0.673 increase in the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County. It was also noted that the P-value for the transformational leadership style coefficient was 0.000, which is less than the set 0.05 significance level, indicating that the transformational leadership style was significant. Based on these results, the study rejected the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between transformational leadership style and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Kitui County. Transformational leaders inspire, expose teachers to training and mentorship which makes them feel appreciated as they also get equipped for future promotions during interviews by the certificates they acquire from various trainings. Transformational leaders work with teachers to overcome challenges within the environs. For instance, by employing teachers paid by the school to help reduce workloads and provision of affordable staff houses, especially in schools far off the towns. Sharing the vision of the institution with teachers brings them onboard to read from the same page and thus remain committed to the course. Emotionally teachers feel appreciated and valued and thus exhibit high levels of continuance dimension of job commitment as they opt to stay in their current workstations. This result is supported by the notion by Aydin and Cilek (2019) that transformational leadership positively influence teachers' job commitment. Fababier and Raymunda (2024) that transformational leadership significantly influence teacher's work performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The transformational leadership approach of principals, assessed through four indicator; intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, idealized influence, and inspirational motivation—positively and significantly impacts teacher performance. The principal offers teachers an inspiring mission and vision, engaging them in reaching established goals. Idealized leaders engage their followers in the decision-making process. They do make key decisions in isolation but they seek for their followers' opinions. Leaders who possess this leadership style are good role models and their followers tend to emulate what their leaders do. The principals however do not practice equality while holding staff meetings and while recommending teachers for further training. Inspirational motivation is most evident when teachers encourage professionalism, embrace innovation, and aim to exceed established expectations. The recommendations are; The Ministry of Education and TSC, along with KEMI, should organize regular in-service training sessions to enhance the transformational leadership skills of principals. Training workshops should emphasize inspiring a collective vision, cultivating innovation, and encouraging teachers to enhance their commitment to work.

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